

Application of Decision Tree based Support Vector Machine in Lung Nodule Classification

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Abstract--- A Computer Aided Detection (CADe) system with a hybrid classifier known as decision tree based Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier is proposed to detect lung nodules in Computed Tomography (CT) images in its early stage. The input images are pre-processed using Gaussian filtering and contrast enhancement technique. Segmentation of lungs is done by performing the operations such as thresholding, area opening and hole filling techniques. The nodules are identified using image subtraction method and the salient features are calculated to differentiate cancerous and non-cancerous nodules using decision tree based SVM classifier. The performance metrics of the proposed classifier is compared with the CAD system with simple SVM. The proposed classifier outperforms the SVM classifier with 92% accuracy, 90% specificity and 98% sensitivity.

Keywords--- Computer Aided Detection (CADe), Lung Nodules, Computed Tomography (CT), Support Vector Machine (SVM).

I. Introduction

The world has seen rapid strides in science and technology in the twentieth century. This is especially true with the detection and diagnosis of cancer with advanced imaging modalities [1]. Cancer is one of the modern-day scourges devouring humanity at an alarming rate. It has no respect for a person's age, social status, region, religion and race [2]. There are various cancer types such as brain cancer, head and neck cancer, lung cancer, pelvic cancer, stomach cancer and so on [3]. Among them, lung cancer is the leading cause of death in cancer related deaths [4]. It has become a major health issue in almost all continents of the world and very severe in Asia, Central America, South America and Africa [5]. By 2020, up to 15 million people worldwide will be diagnosed with cancer of various forms every year, with 70% of these new cases occurring in the developing world.

When one uses modern day techniques such as such as Computed Tomography (CT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), Single Photon Emission Computer Tomography (SPECT) [6] or a combination of techniques such as PET-CT, along with Computer Aided Detection (CAD) systems, the detection of cancer at an early stage becomes a real possibility [7]. If it is detected quite early, the survival rate of the patients becomes higher with up to 70% survival for a period of 5 years [8]. In this regard, advancements in CAD systems are the need of the hour for health professionals to effectively fight against cancer.

According to the formal definition of a pulmonary lung nodule, it is a focal opacity with a diameter of 3 to 30 mm. If they are much smaller than 3 mm, they are micro-nodules and macro-nodules (mass) are those whose sizes exceed that of 30 mm [9]. With respect to their location, they are classified as small nodules, ground glass opacity nodules, juxta-pleural nodules which are attached to the lung wall and juxta-vascular nodules, attached with blood vessels [10]. The nodules can be solids, semi-solids and in some rare cases, non-solids [11].

The patients with lung cancer undergo chest CT examination in the beginning. These images are analysed by medical physicists [12]. They have an important role to play in correctly diagnosing the patients with pulmonary lung nodules. According to standard international guidelines, it is imperative to make sure that these procedures, especially with respect to analyse the CT images requires competent professionals capable of making as little error as possible [13].

Humanely speaking, errors may creep in if the medical physicists are overloaded due to the amount of increased scanning being carried out in the recent years [14]. Manual methods, thus, are prone to the risks of errors due to various factors such as human visual system, insufficient training to medical physicists and fatigue associated with them [15]. Grounded on this motivation, automated methods have been developed over the years and have now become quite popular and ubiquitous because of their versatility.

CAD systems are categorized into two types. Computer Aided Detection system (CADe) is the first category. The second category is Computer Aided Diagnosis system (CADx). This work dwells on the first category, i.e., CADe system [16]. CADe systems play a vital role in reducing the workload of medical physicists. With CADe systems, it is possible to screen more number of patients within a short span of time. It is possible to increase the pulmonary lung nodule detection accuracy [11].

A typical CADe system has the following steps. Pre-processing, lung segmentation, pulmonary nodule detection and its classification [17]. Preprocessing techniques are essentially used for noise removal and adjustment of contrast. These include Morphology Operation [18], Streak Detection Filter[19], 2D enhancement filters[20], Isotropic resampling [21], Cylinder Filter and Spherical Filter [22,23]. Some of the recent techniques used are Type II fuzzy algorithm by F.V.Farhani et al., [24] and Bi-cubic interpolation by Jing Gong et al., [25].

The next step in a CADe system is the lung segmentation. Some of the techniques used previously are Negative Masking [26], Linear discriminant analysis [27], Region growing algorithm with active contour model [28] and Genetic cellular neural network [29]. Recently, Ezhil E. Nithila et al., have used new active contour model with new signed pressure function for segmentation of lungs [30]. The third step is the detection of pulmonary nodules. This has been effectively carried out by 3D labelling method [18], Laplacian filters [19] and Surface normal overlap [26]. In 2016, MuzzamilJavaid et al., have used K-means clustering and morphological opening for the same [31].

To eliminate false positives (FP), classifiers are finally used after the successful detection of candidate pulmonary nodules. Based on intensity, shape and texture, these FPs have been eliminated. Some of the frequently used classifiers are Linear Discriminant Analysis [27,32,33,34] and Rule Based Classification [27,35,36,37,38]. One of the recent technique is a multi-view convolutional neural networks used by Arnaud A.A. Setio et al [39]. Artificial neural network is also one of the most commonly used classifiers reported in the recent literature [40].

This research work focuses on the usage of some modern-day algorithms to detect the pulmonary lung nodules aka cancer tissues in the lungs at an early stage and increase the efficiency of CADe system in order to help the patients to get early treatment for lung cancer.

II. Materials and Methods

The proposed system for lung nodule classification consists of data acquisition, pre-processing, lung parenchyma segmentation, potential nodule detection, area-based filtering, feature extraction and classification. The framework of the proposed CADe system is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flow Chart of the Proposed Methodology

Data Acquisition

The lung CT images used for training and validating the proposed CADe system are taken from the publicly available database called Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC). The images are of DICOM format with resolution of 512 x 512 pixels. These images are annotated by 4 expert radiologists. Totally, 1018 cases are present in the database. For this work, 30 cases have been selected. The sizes of the cancerous nodules are assumed to be between 3 and 30mm. For executing the proposed CADe system, MATLAB 2016b is used. A sample CT image from LIDC database is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: A Sample Input Image from LIDC Database

Preprocessing

The preliminary step in the CADe system is pre-processing. During image acquisition, noise might have added in to the image. This noise is removed using Gaussian Filtering. Also, due to less contrast, the CT image looks very dull and the object of interest is not clearly visible. The contrast of the entire image is adjusted by the contrast enhancement process. It is done based on the intensity value between 0.2-0.9. The pre-processed image of the proposed system is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Pre-processed Image

Lung Segmentation

The main objective of segmentation is to make easy or change the description of an image into something that is more relevant and simpler to analyse. Based on texture, colour, intensity, the pixels available in the area share the similar characteristics. Regions of adjacent area are more over dissimilar with respect to the same features. The segmentation method used in this work is a combination of thresholding, area opening and hole filling techniques. The thresholding operation is done on the pre-processed image. The area opening removes small objects from the image that have less than 6000 pixels with 8-connectivity. Thus, the lung parenchyma without nodules is extracted.

Byhole filling method, the lung mask has been created. The lung mask and thresholded image are multiplied to get lung parenchyma with nodules. The segmented lung is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Segmented Lungs

Candidate Nodule Detection

For identifying all the nodules and nodule like structures, the negative image of lung parenchyma with nodules is obtained. Also, the negative image of lung parenchyma without nodules is obtained. Then, the negative image of lung parenchyma with nodules is subtracted from the negative image of lung parenchyma without nodules. The potential nodule candidates are shown in Figure 5. In this step, all the nodule like structures are identified. But all the identified nodules are not real nodules.

Figure 5: Potential Nodules

Area Based Filtering and Nodule Labelling

To reduce the false positive nodules, area-based filtering is done. This method removes objects (nodules) that do not meet the criterion. The criterion is the number of pixels of the object should lie between 11.3 pixels to 113 pixels. The area based filtered nodules are shown in Figure 6.

Then each nodule is extracted separately. The default connectivity used in the experiment is 8. The detected nodules are labelled individually and masked with the original gray image to get gray scale nodules. The individual nodules and the corresponding labels are listed in Table 1.

Figure 6: Filtered Nodules Using Area-based Method

Table 1: Individual Nodules with Labels

S. No.	Nodule Representation	Binary image	Gray image
1	Nodule No.1		
2	Nodule No.2		
3	Nodule No.3		
4	Nodule No.4		
5	Nodule No.5		

Feature Extraction

In order to identify whether the nodules are cancerous or non-cancerous, the features such as maximum intensity, mean intensity, variance and entropy are calculated for individual candidate nodules. These numerical feature vectors are given as input to the classifier. In Figure 7, the average value of the feature values of the nodules is shown. In this bar chart, the variation of the features for cancerous and non-cancerous are clearly depicted. It is shown that, the feature ‘‘Variance’’ is significant which differentiates the cancerous and non-cancerous nodules.

Figure 7: Variation of Feature Values between Cancerous and Non-cancerous Nodules

Classification

Classification is the final stage in a CAde system. This distinguishes the cancerous nodules from the non-cancerous nodules based on the input feature vectors. Initially, the classification using SVM is done which gives some good accuracy. But when the result from the decision tree has been given as input to SVM, it gives out result with even better accuracy. In the decision tree based SVM, the features are given to the decision tree and then it classifies as non-cancerous or cancerous. This result is given to SVM because SVM needs the database as to which feature set corresponds to cancerous and which are those corresponds to the non-cancerous. But when we filter out the features using decision tree, the point gets clear. The SVM learns which features corresponds to cancerous and which are not cancerous. It is like learning from previous experience of the other. Thus, SVM gets trained from the preceded one, the decision tree. The performance of SVM classifier without decision tree and the proposed classifier known as decision tree based SVM classifier is compared.

Performance Metrics

To know the performance of the classifiers, the following measures have been calculated. They are accuracy, specificity and sensitivity [31]. These parameters depend on the true positive, false positive, true negative and false negative values.

The parameter accuracy defines the relationship between true positives, true negatives, false positives and false negatives [31].

$$Accuracy = \frac{True\ Positive + True\ Negative}{True\ Positive + False\ Positive + True\ Negative + False\ Negative} \tag{1}$$

The parameter specificity is defined as follows.

$$Specificity = \frac{True\ Negative}{True\ Negative + False\ Positive} \tag{2}$$

The parameter sensitivity is defined as follows.

$$Sensitivity = \frac{True\ Positive}{True\ Positive + False\ Negative} \tag{3}$$

Table 2: Comparison between SVM Classifier and Proposed Decision Tree based SVM Classifier

Performance Metrics	SVM	Decision tree based SVM
Accuracy	90%	92%
Specificity	88%	90%
Sensitivity	95%	98%

III. Results and Discussion

In this section, the results obtained from SVM classifier and proposed classifier is discussed. To test the CADe system, the images are obtained from LIDC database. Totally 30 cases are used from this database. Among these 30 cases, 80% of images are used for training and 20% of images are used for testing. The nodules with pixels ranges from 11.3 to 113 are considered in this research work.

The lung region is segmented using the combined operations such as thresholding, area opening and hole filling. From the segmented lung parenchyma region, the potential candidate nodules are identified. Area based filtering has reduced the non-nodules considerably. The nodules are individually identified using connectivity and labelling procedure. The features are extracted from the individual nodules. In order to classify the nodules into two classes namely cancerous or non-cancerous, the features from the nodules are used to train the Support Vector Machine. Using test images, the performance of SVM and decision tree-based SVM are validated. The result shows that the decision tree based SVM classifier has good accuracy, specificity and sensitivity. The performance metrics of these classifiers are listed in Table 2.

IV. Conclusion

The proposed method presents a CADe system for the detection of lung nodule. Thresholding along with area opening and hole filling were used for lung segmentation. Using the difference operation between lung parenchyma with nodules and without nodules images, all the candidate nodules were identified. The nodules are detected based on area of each detected nodules. Statistical and intensity features were extracted for better understanding. To reduce the false positives, SVM and decision tree based SVM, were used. The performance of SVM has been compared with the proposed classifier called decision tree based SVM. The proposed classifier has less number of false positives and has greater sensitivity, specificity and accuracy.

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